

Bromination of Lactic Acid and Calcium Lactate in Presence of Light.

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It is known already that bromine reacts with lactic acid in light (Ciusa and Piergallini, *Atti R. Accad. Lincei*, (5), 23, 237, 1914) to give pyruvic acid according to equation :

This investigation was begun with the object of finding out how the velocity constant of the photo-bromination varies with the intensity, frequency and the state of polarisation of incident light.

EXPERIMENT.

The experimental arrangement will be clear from Fig. 1.

The light-source L was a Point-o-lita arc lamp of 100 c. p. run from a battery maintained at 110 volts. C was a convex lens placed at a distance from the lamp equal to the focal length so as to obtain a parallel beam of light.

F is a water-filter, M is a Wratten monochromatic blue or green filter as the case may be. The reaction-vessel R was made of plane-parallel glass sides with a closed stopper at the top and was placed inside a double-jacketted copper box B with an opening on side. By continuous circulation of water through the copper box from

a thermostat by means of a pump, the temperature was maintained constant within $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Merck's chemically pure lactic acid was taken and made into $\frac{N}{10}$ solution. A deci-normal solution of bromine redistilled in the laboratory was prepared from time to time.

The rate of reaction was measured iodometrically by taking out 2 cc. of the solution from the reaction vessel at different intervals of time after exposure to light. Redistilled water was used throughout the experiments.

The results obtained in the case of photo-bromination of lactic acid were somewhat irregular and Tables I, II and III show the best results obtained.

TABLE I.

Temperature— 35.0° . Wave-length limit : 490–530 $\mu\mu$.

Initial concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{30}$.

Initial concentration of lactic acid $\frac{N}{30}$.

Time in mins.	Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{100}$	Monomolecular velocity-constants.
0	5.55 c.c.	...
25	5.0	.00181
75	4.1	.00175
125	3.25	.00186
177	2.1	.00235

TABLE II.

Temp. 35°C. Wave-length limit : 440 - 500 μ Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{30}$.Initial concentration of lactic acid $\frac{N}{30}$.

Time in mins	Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{30}$	Monomolecular velocity constants.
0	4.9 cc	...
25	4.8	0.0227
75	3.45	0.0203
101	2.25	0.0210
136	1.95	0.0204

TABLE III.

Temp. 35°C. Dark reaction.

Initial composition of the solution - same as in Tables I and II.

Time in mins	Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{100}$	Monomolecular velocity constants
0	5.8 cc	
30	5.25	0.0135
64	4.75	0.0137
94	4.5	0.0117
150	4.1	0.0100

It is thus clear that there is a considerable dark reaction which accounts for about $\frac{2}{3}$ of the observed reaction.

The photo-chemical efficiency of light is not thus capable of very exact measurement as the velocity of pure photo-chemical reaction is always the difference between the observed light reaction and the dark reaction.

The idea of measuring the velocity of reaction for the same intensity of plane polarised and circularly polarised light was, therefore, abandoned, as the results that would be obtained in those cases could never be considered very trustworthy.

*Application of Einstein's Law of Photo-chemical
Equivalence.*

The intensity of the radiations was measured by a thermopile with a low resistance sensitive galvanometer by comparison with a standard Heffner lamp and was found for blue light to be 13×900 ergs per sq. cm. per sec. and for green light 12.7×900 ergs sq. cm. per sec.

Number of gm. mole of bromine transformed by absorbed light per sec. per sq. cm. of surface $\times$ the depth of the reaction vessel (2.5 cm.) :—

Taking the results of Table I where the change is .55 c.c. $\frac{N}{100}$ in 2 c.c. of the solution in the first 25 minutes and remembering that only one-third of the total reaction velocity is due to absorption of light, the above comes out to be

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{.0055}{2 \times 2} \times \frac{1}{25 \times 60} \times \frac{1}{1000} \times 2.5 \text{ gm. mols. per sec.} \\ & = 7.6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ gm. mols. per sec.} \\ & = 7.6 \times 10^{-10} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23} \text{ mols. per sec.} \\ & = 46.4 \times 10^{13} \text{ mols. per sec.} \end{aligned}$$

Now, according to Noddak 70% of the incident blue or green light is absorbed by the bromine solution and thus the energy absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. is $13 \times 900 \times .7$

ergs. the frequency of the energy employed $\frac{3 \times 10^{10}}{500 \times 10^{-7}}$

Hence the number of quanta of energy absorbed

$$= 13 \times 900 \times .7 \times \frac{500 \times 10^{-7}}{3 \times 10^{10}} \times \frac{1}{6.5 \times 10^{-27}}$$

$$= 210 \times 10^{13}$$

Four quanta of energy, therefore, activated one molecule of bromine and Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence appears not to hold here.

Bromination of Calcium Lactate.

The bromination of lactic acid sometimes gave irregular results and it was apprehended that the lactic acid used might not have been absolutely pure. A pure salt of lactic acid was, therefore, tried and calcium lactate was selected as it is easy to purify by repeated crystallisations.

Experimental data are given in Tables IV and V.

TABLE IV.

Temp. 35°C. Wave-length limit : 490-530 $\mu\mu$.

Initial conc. of bromine $\frac{N}{30}$.

Initial conc. of calcium lactate $\frac{N}{30}$.

Time in mins.	Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{100}$.	Monomolecular velocity constants.
0	6.45 c.c.	...
24	4.65	.00592
48	3.35	.00593
72	2.35	.00609
96	1.65	.00617

TABLE V.

Temp. 35°C. Wave-length limit. 490-530 $\mu\mu$.Initial concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{15}$.Initial concentration of calcium lactate $\frac{N}{30}$.

Time in mins.	Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{100}$	Monomolecular velocity constants.
0	11.35	..
10	9.80 1.55	.00638
20	8.35 1.45	.00661
30	6.95 1.40	.00710
40	5.55 1.40	.00770

Table IV indicates that the reaction is monomolecular. If the initial concentration of calcium lactate be raised to $\frac{N}{15}$, keeping the bromine concentration constant, the velocity constant increases to .00925 and very good constants are obtained at this concentration as well.

Table VI gives the velocity-constants for increased concentration of calcium lactate.

TABLE VI.

Temperature 35°C. Wave-length limit. 490-530 $\mu\mu$.Initial concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{30}$.Initial concentration of calcium lactate $\frac{N}{15}$.

Time in mins	Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{100}$	Monomolecular velocity constants.
0	6.15 c.c.	..
12	4.7	.00935
29	3.35	.00910
44	2.35	.00927
59	1.75	.00925

Such result is indeed to be expected. Bromine is here the photo-active molecule. It gets excited by absorption of light and if within its life-period of excitation it collides with an acceptor calcium lactate molecule reaction will take place. The velocity of reaction should necessarily be greater, the greater the concentration of acceptor molecule and will reach a maximum limit when the concentration of the acceptor molecule is so high that all the activated bromine molecules will have an opportunity of colliding with calcium lactate molecules within its life-period of excitation.

Increase in the concentration of bromine makes the velocity constant irregular as will be apparent from Table V. The reaction tends to degenerate into a zero molecular one. If we assume that the velocity of reaction is essentially governed by the rate of production of excited bromine molecules then

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kI_0(1 - e^{-\epsilon c})$$

where I_0 is the intensity of incident light and ϵ the extinction co-efficient of bromine. For small values of C ,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= kI_0[1 - e^{-\epsilon c}] \\ &= kI_0\epsilon c \end{aligned}$$

Hence the reaction is monomolecular. For large values of C , $e^{-\epsilon c}$ is negligibly small and $\frac{dx}{dt} = kI_0$, *i.e.*, the reaction is zero-molecular.

TABLE VII.
Temperature 35.0°C.
Wave-length 440-500 $\mu\mu$.

Initial conc. of Br.	Initial con. of cal. lactate	Monomolecular velocity constants.
$\frac{N}{30}$	$\frac{N}{30}$	·00633
$\frac{N}{30}$	$\frac{N}{15}$	00947
$\frac{N}{15}$	$\frac{N}{30}$	·00660—·00792 *

* The velocity constants are irregular and the reaction tends to become a zero-molecular one.

TABLE VIII.
Temperature 35°C.
Initial concentration of Br. $\frac{N}{30}$.

Initial concentration of calcium lactate $\frac{N}{30}$.

Dark Reaction.

Time in mins.	Concentration of bromine $\frac{N}{100}$.	Monomolecular velocity constants.
0	6·15 c.c.	...
20	4·95	·00472
41	4·10	·00467
60	3·20	·00472
92	2·30	·00464

Velocity of Dark Reaction.—Table VIII gives the velocity of dark reaction at 35°C. It will be seen from comparison with Table IV that about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the velocity constant is due to dark reaction. It is curious that the dark reaction where the concentration of the reacting molecules of bromine and of calcium lactate are comparable should give a mono-molecular velocity constant and not a bimolecular one.

Application of Einstein's Law.

Number of quanta of energy absorbed = 21.0×10^{14} .

A. For calcium lactate concentration $\cdot \frac{N}{30}$.

Number of gm. mols. transformed by light per second per sq. cm. $\times$ depth of reaction vessel, taking the results of Table IV.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{.018}{2 \times 2} \times \frac{1}{24 \times 60} \times \frac{1}{1000} \times 2.5 \text{ gm. mols.} \\ & = 20 \times 10^{-10} \text{ gm. mols.} \\ & = 12.6 \times 10^{14} \text{ molecules.} \end{aligned}$$

[One-fourth of the observed velocity in this case being due to light, *vide* Tables IV and VIII.]

B. For calcium lactate concentration $\dots \dots \frac{N}{15}$.

Number of gm. mols. transformed by light per sec. per sq. cm. $\times$ depth of reaction vessel, taking the results of Table VI.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{.0145}{2 \times 2} \times \frac{1}{12 \times 60} \times \frac{1}{1000} \times 2.5 \text{ gm. mols.} \\ & = .333 \times 10^{-8} \text{ gm. mols.} \\ & = .333 \times 10^{-8} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23} \text{ molecules} \\ & = 20.31 \times 10^{14} \text{ molecules.} \end{aligned}$$

We thus find that when the concentration of acceptor molecule of calcium lactate is small, *viz.*, $\frac{N}{30}$, about two quanta is necessary for the transformation of one molecule of calcium lactate. But as the concentration of calcium lactate is increased to $\frac{N}{15}$, about one quantum is necessary for the transformation of one molecule of calcium lactate.

This result is in agreement with the observation of Noddak (*Zeit. für Electrochemie*, 1921, 27, 359) who showed that as the concentration of CCl_4Br in CCl_4 is diminished, the photo-chemical efficiency of the chlorination process diminishes as given in the Table IX enclosed.

TABLE IX.

Dilution $\text{CCl}_4\text{Br} : \text{CCl}_4$	Br. liberated as observed : Br.- change as calculated from Einstein's Law.
1 : 2	.90
1 : 16	.39
1 : 64	.071

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Fig I

